

Perceived Influence of Blended Teaching on Postgraduate Educational Management Students Learning in Rivers State Universities

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Abstract

The study investigated perceived influence of blended teaching on postgraduate educational management students learning in Rivers State Universities. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study is 58. It consists of all lecturers in the Department of Educational Management in Rivers State owned universities. The sample size of the study was 58. Census sampling technique was used to sample the entire population of the study. A structured questionnaire titled perceived influence of blended teaching of postgraduate students learning questionnaire was used as instrument for data collection. Three experts validated the instructed and Cronbach Alpha Method was used to obtain an average reliability coefficient of 0.83. 58 copies of the questionnaire were administered, retrieved, and used for the study. The items were rated on a four (4) point rating scale; mean and standard deviation was used to analyze the research questions while z-test was used in testing the formulated hypotheses. The findings reviewed that, Educational Management postgraduate students learning was influenced by face-to-face and hybrid teaching to a high extent. The researcher recommended that lecturers should ensure that students or learners became active and not passive participants as this will help or make postgraduate Educational Management students to develop knowledge on their own and confident without the interference of the instructor or lecturer and measures should be adopted by lecturers on how online learning instruction could be used to achieve Educational Management courses having psychomotor objectives in Rivers State owned universities.

Keywords: *Blended Teaching, Postgraduate, Educational Management, Learning.*

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Introduction

Teaching is one of the instruments through which individuals are educated and is always intended to lead to some learning. Hart (2017) opined that, it is an arrangement and manipulation of a situation in which there are gaps and obstructions which an individual will seek to overcome and from which he will learn in the course of doing so. Hart further asserted that, it is a system of actions intended to produce learning. Teaching is therefore, the art of assisting others to learn which includes the provision of information (instruction) and of appropriate situation, conditions or activities design to facilitate teaching (Ayeni, 2013). With the arrival of new Information and

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Communication Technologies (ICT), the whole educational system has undergone dramatic changes within the past two decades. These technologies have improved approaches to education especially in teaching. As Bonk (2016) claims, anyone can now learn anything from anyone at any time. Blended learning is emerging as one of the most promising instructional practices in the educational settings. The pedagogy of using a blended learning approach assumes that the learner is engaged in the face-to-face interactions as well as benefitting the virtual or online platform (Poon, 2014).

According to Lin, Tseng & Chiang (2017) blended teaching are defined as a mix of the traditional face-to-face and the hybrid teaching so that instruction occurs both in the classroom and online. This connotes an extension of the face-to-face learning that makes students off task more often because lecturers and students' activities are centered around the classroom for either discussion or group project, on the other end, virtual learning gives the student a platform to work on individual task that are insulated from intrusion. In the same vein, Keller (2012) defined blended teaching as the effective integration of different modes of delivery, modes of teaching and styles of learning as a result of adopting a strategic and systematic approach to use technology combined with the best features of face-to-face instruction which allows students to define their own learning and to select learning materials by themselves. According to Sun & Chen (2016) the process of teaching does not confine itself with mere classroom interaction or presentation of the content, teaching material or learning experiences. A teaching task therefore can never be confined to the face-to-face dialogue between the teacher and the students carried out in the interaction phase, but it begins even before the teacher enters the classroom with the work of planning the teaching task, and continues after the interaction phase in the form of evaluation, feedback and similar other post-active activities, many times even after the teacher leaves the class (Sucre, 2015). This is applicable in teaching all subjects and courses in various specialized areas including Educational Management courses.

Educational Management courses are taught in tertiary institutions of learning. Technology has helped to change perception of many things. It, therefore, implies that Educational Management as a course of study has to move with time. Nwankwo (2013) viewed Educational Management as a field which is concerned with the operation of educational organizations. It is the process of planning, organizing and directing activities in a school, effectively utilizing human and material resources, in order to accomplish the schools' objectives. Educational management is both a field of academic study and a collective group of professionals that includes principals, teachers, and other education professionals (Torrington, Hall, Taylor & Alkinson, 2013). In order to teach Educational Management courses effectively both at undergraduate and postgraduate level; a carefully developed, structured and self-guided teaching materials can be delivered through various but appropriate technologies (Poon, 2013). These technologies include the hardware, software and courseware. The hardware systems are the physical parts or components such as system units, printers, scanners, CD/DVD moderns, multimedia projectors, interactive boards among others that are used to process, store as well as run the software applications while the software (which include system software, application software and utility programs) are the written codes or instructions that control and direct the activities of the computer system. The courseware on the other hand refers to electronic instructional packages such as Marvis Beacon, Typing Tutor, Professor Teaches and so on used for teaching purposes especially for the purpose of acquiring knowledge, skills and attitudes required for successful school to work transition. This courseware can take different formats such as animated instructions, audio-visual instruction and audio instruction among others which can be combined differently by the teacher in order to implement a meaningful but successful blended learning in form of e-learning, online learning, m-learning and so on. Nicholas (2019) is of the view that for higher education course like Educational Management at postgraduate level, blended teaching has become the reality characterized by continuous

investigation and debates of the benefits, potential and effectiveness to transform and improve the teaching process. New highly interactive meaningful and student-centered blended learning environments have been developed and fostered by the current and advanced technologies. The convergence of traditional face-to-face and distributed learning environment that were sharply separated in the past has been in progress by developing blended learning environment. Different media/method combinations and the needs of different audiences have enabled the approach of face-to-face practiced in a lecturer-centered environment and person-to-person classroom activities, and distance learning system based on self-paced learning. Hence, this necessitates the use of blended teaching for postgraduate students of Educational Management.

Statement of the Problem

With the proliferation of information and communication technology tools and its application in education, teaching and learning at the postgraduate level ought to have been on the high side to commensurate with the pace of developmental explosion in the knowledge economy since it is not clashed or loaded with many courses as compared to the undergraduate. It has been observed that in teaching Educational Management courses at Postgraduate level students still struggle to understand what is being taught and most cases often become frustrated and discouraged. Courses taught using the traditional method move all students through the curriculum at the same pace, regardless of mastery (Lin, Tseng & Chiang, 2017). The course lecturer has little time to assist individual students, and at home students have no one to turn to for assistance. At postgraduate level, students are supposed to learn even at the comfort of their homes and offices, but the reverse is the case.

These problems can be averted with blended learning approach through the face-to-face instruction, on-line instruction, self-paced learning instruction, virtual collaboration among others. With the growing knowledge in ICT and the growing interest in technological innovation, learning has taken a new dimension beyond face-to-face learning, making teaching more flexible. Also, in the era of COVID 19 pandemic when universities were closed, it was expected that blended learning instruction should have been used. To this end, this study will investigate the extent to which blended learning influence the teaching of Educational Management Postgraduate Students in Rivers State owned Universities?

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to examine perceived influence of blended teaching on Postgraduate Educational Management students learning in Rivers State universities.

Specifically, the study sought to find out:

1. The extent to which face-to-face teaching influence Postgraduate Educational Management students learning in Rivers State Universities.
2. The extent to which hybrid teaching influence Postgraduate Educational Management students learning in Rivers State Universities.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent does face-to-face teaching influence Postgraduate Educational Management students' learning in Rivers State Universities?
3. To what extent does hybrid teaching influence Postgraduate Educational Management students' learning in Rivers State Universities?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Lecturers on the extent to which face-to-face teaching influence Postgraduate Educational Management students learning in Rivers State universities.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Lecturers on the extent to which hybrid teaching influence Postgraduate Educational Management students learning in Rivers State Universities.

Concept of Blended Teaching

The concept of blended teaching has been around for not so long time, but its terminology was not firmly established until around the beginning of the 21st century. The term blended teaching is now commonly used particularly in corporate and higher education settings. Educators have grappled with the concept for ages and now the convergence of the global economy and information and technology has produced an environment in which the medium for instruction could change (Gumbo, Magonde & Nhamo, 2017). Blended learning can be defined as learning systems that combine face-to-face instruction with computer mediated instruction (Crane, 2017). It involves a combination of conventional face-to-face and online technology-based learning (Summers & Dan, 2012). The term blended learning as stated is not a new concept, but a recent addition to the lexicon of the education profession. Blended learning is referred to as hybrid and mixed teaching and it is used in very different ways by many researchers.

According to Sylvester (2013) blended teaching is an education model which can integrate e-learning and can improve in parallel with the new technological development with traditional face-to-face teaching and provides integration in the classroom. Similarly, Bicen, Ozdamli & Uzunboylu (2012) asserted that blended learning instruction approach is a combination of face-to-face teaching activities that are integrated in a planned pedagogically valuable way and where some of the face-to-face classroom interaction is replaced by online activities. Blended learning is an innovative type of education carried out by combining the positive aspects of different learning approaches. It provides a big convenience for the course to achieve its target by combining the face-to-face interaction in traditional teaching and providing accessibility to instruction in time and in space with embodied enrichment in materials provided by web-based teaching and or mediated instruction (Heinze, 2014).

Furthermore, Thorne (2013) describes blended teaching as a method of instruction that combines online with face-to-face learning activities that are integrated in a planned, pedagogically valuable way and where some of the face-to-face is replaced by online activities. Blended teaching is a new type of education prepared for a certain group by combining the positive aspects of different learning approaches. The combination may involve mixing various event-based activities such as face-to-face classroom, live e-learning, self-paced learning, synchronous online conference and training, or asynchronous self-pace learning (Sadiku, Musa & Nelatury 2017). Blended learning will provide a big convenience for the course to achieve its target by combining the face-to-face interaction in traditional learning and time; place and material richness provided by web-based learning.

Face-to-Face Teaching and Learning

Face-to-face teaching is an instructional method where course content and learning material are taught in person to a group of students. This allows for a live interaction between a learner and an instructor, it is the most traditional type of learning instruction. Learners benefit from a greater level of interaction with their fellow students as well. During face-to-face learning, students are

held accountable for their progress at the class, especially meeting date and time (Oweis, 2018). Face-to-face teaching ensures a better understanding and recollection of lesson content and gives class members a chance to bond with one another.

Bollger and Wasilik (2019) averred that face-to-face teaching is essentially a teacher-centered method of education and tends to vary widely among cultures. Many modern education systems have largely shifted away from traditional face-to-face forms of educational instruction, in favour of individual students' needs. Traditional (Face-to-Face) teaching focuses on several elements, including lectures, capstones, team projects, labs, studios, and so forth. In the view of Garrison and Kanuka (2015) teaching is conducted synchronously in a physical learning environment (utilizing appropriate safety measures), meaning that traditionally, the students are in the same place simultaneously. The traditional classroom has the significant advantage of face-to-face interaction between the students and the educator and the students themselves. Students derive motivation from the teacher as well as from the other students. In a traditional lecture-style class, information is sometimes fed to the student and then passed back to the instructor through written proctored assessments. Students have found that the face-to-face classroom can be an active learning environment (Nolan, Hayden & Maisbary, 2019). The learning space is also physical (utilizing appropriate safety measures), as both the student and instructor can see, hear, and pick up on physical cues and body language.

Hybrid Teaching and Learning

Hybrid teaching is education that takes place over the Internet. It is often referred to as “eLearning” among other terms. However, hybrid teaching is just one type of “distance learning” - the umbrella term for any learning that takes place across distance and not in a traditional classroom (Sun & Chen, 2016). Hybrid teaching is a method of education whereby students of education learn in a fully virtual environment. First introduced in the 1990s with the creation of the internet and utilized in distance learning, hybrid teaching is most prevalent in higher education, enabling students from different geographical areas to engage with an academic institution and other students online and learn flexibly, at their own pace, while working towards a degree or certificate (Summers & Dan, 2012). A learning system based on formalized teaching but with the help of electronic devices is online learning. It can be termed as a network enabled transfer of skills and knowledge, and the delivery of education is made to a large number of recipients at the same or different times. Earlier, it was not accepted wholeheartedly as it was assumed that this system lacked the human element required in learning (Crane, 2017).

Hybrid teaching refers to an internet-based teaching environment that can connect students of diverse backgrounds who boast different perspectives. It is the type of education that requires computers, laptops, or smartphones, and a high-speed internet connection. Hybrid teaching is also used in schools and colleges. The method is beneficial in cases where students are living in a remote location. Working professionals who do not have the time to attend a class physically prefer learning online. Individuals who wish to enhance their skill set but do not have the time or resources also engage in this type of education (Sadiku, Musa & Nelatury, 2017).

Methodology

Design of the Study

The study adopted a descriptive. This study was carried out in Rivers State. The population of the study is 58. It consists of all lecturers in the Department of Educational Management in Rivers State owned universities. As the time of this study, Rivers State owned universities have 58 Educational Management lecturers (RSU=22 and IAUE=36). The sample size of the study was 58.

Census sampling technique was used to sample the entire population of the study. The instrument for data collection was titled; Influence of Blended Teaching of Postgraduate Students Learning Questionnaire (IBTPGSLQ). The instrument was designed by the researcher. The instrument had two sections, A and B. Section A had items designed to review personal information about the respondents. Section B had two clusters with 5 items each which focused on answering the research questions. The response format adopted was a four-point rating scale as follows: Very High Extent (VHE=4), High Extent (HE=3), LE (Low Extent=2) and Very Low Extent (VLE=1). The instrument was subjected to face and content validation by three experts; one from the Department of Educational Management and two from the Department of Measurement and Evaluation in the Faculty of Education, the questionnaire was administered on 10 lecturers outside the Department of study from RSU and IAUE. The analysis of the scores in the two sets was carried out using Cronbach Alpha method. The computation of the scores yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.84 and 0.81 respectively. The reliability coefficient showed the instrument was reliable. The researcher through the help of her trained research assistant administered the questionnaire directly to the respondents. Data collected from the respondents were analyzed using Mean and Standard Deviation. To test the significance of the two null hypotheses formulated for this study at 0.05, z-test was used. The formulated null hypotheses were rejected when the calculated z value is greater than or equals to the z-critical value of ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and failed to reject null hypotheses when the z-calculated value is less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

To what extent does face-to-face teaching influence Postgraduate Educational Management students learning in Rivers State Universities?

Table 1. Mean Responses of RSU and IAUE Lecturers on the Extent Face-to-Face Teaching Influence Postgraduate Educational Management Students Learning

S/No	Items	RSU Lecturers		Decision	IAUE Lecturers		Decision
		—	SD		—	SD	
		X			X		
1	Face-to-face instruction encourages the sharing of knowledge	3.05	0.97	HE	2.86	1.09	HE
2	Face-to-face learning builds confidence of teachers and learners	2.95	1.02	HE	2.94	0.99	HE
3	Face-to-face instruction enhances teacher/student interaction on the subject matter	3.14	0.96	HE	2.75	1.03	HE
4	It is used in solving analytical problems	2.91	0.99	HE	2.78	0.92	HE
5	Face-to-face learning instruction is used to obtain reactions and feedbacks from students	3.23	1.86	HE	2.72	1.00	HE
	Grand Mean/SD	3.06	1.16	HE	2.81	1.01	HE

Source: Researcher's Field Result, 2024.

Table 1 above shows that Educational Management Postgraduate students learning was influenced by face-to-face teaching to a high extent with the following mean values for items (1-5) for RSU

Lecturers: 3.05, 2.95, 3.14, 2.91 and 3.23 and for IAUE Lecturers: 2.86, 2.94, 2.75, 2.78 and 2.72 respectively.

Research Question 2

To what extent does hybrid teaching influence Postgraduate Educational Management students learning in Rivers State Universities?

Table 2. Mean Responses of RSU and IAUE Lecturers on the Extent Hybrid Teaching Influence Postgraduate Educational Management Students Learning

S/No	Items	RSU Lecturers		Decision	IAUE Lecturers		Decision
		— X	SD		— X	SD	
6	Hybrid teaching promotes multiple interactions among lecturers and the students	3.32	0.81	HE	2.97	0.96	HE
7	Hybrid teaching encourages the sharing of knowledge	3.09	0.90	HE	2.56	1.01	HE
8	It makes teaching and learning more flexible	3.14	0.69	HE	2.86	1.06	HE
9	It provides equal opportunities for discussion to introverts and extroverts	3.00	1.00	HE	2.67	1.05	HE
10	Hybrid teaching increase interaction between the teachers and the students	3.41	0.69	HE	2.89	1.02	HE
	Grand Mean/SD	3.19	0.82	HE	2.79	1.02	HE

Source: Researcher's Field Result, 2024.

Table 2 above shows that Educational Management Postgraduate students learning was influenced by hybrid teaching to a high extent with the following mean values for items (6-10) for RSU Lecturers: 3.32, 3.09, 3.14, 3.00 and 3.41 and for IAUE Lecturers: 2.97, 2.56, 2.86, 2.67 and 2.89 respectively.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Lecturers on the extent to which face-to-face teaching influence Postgraduate Educational Management students learning in Rivers State Universities.

Table 3. Z-Test Analysis of the Responses on the Influence of Face-to-Face Teaching of Postgraduate Educational Management Students Learning

Respondents	N	— X	SD	DF	LS	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
RSU Lecturers	22	3.06	1.16	56	0.05	0.83	±1.96	Failed to reject no significant difference
IAUE Lecturers	36	2.81	1.01					

Source: Researcher's Field Result, 2024.

Table 3 above shows no significant difference in the mean responses of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Lecturers on the extent to which face-to-face teaching influence Postgraduate Educational Management students learning in Rivers State Universities. The z-calculated value of 0.83 was less than the z-critical value of ±1.96 ($0.83 \leq \pm 1.96$) for degree of

freedom of 56 at .05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted which states that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Lecturers on the extent to which face-to-face teaching influence Postgraduate Educational Management students learning in Rivers State Universities.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Lecturers on the extent to which hybrid teaching influence Postgraduate Educational Management students learning in Rivers State Universities.

Table 4. Z-Test Analysis of the Responses on the Influence of Hybrid Teaching on Postgraduate Educational Management Students Learning

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	DF	LS	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
RSU Lecturers	22	3.19	0.82	56	0.05	1.67	± 1.96	Failed to reject no significant difference
IAUE Lecturers	36	2.79	1.02					

Source: Researcher's Field Result, 2024.

Table 4 above shows no significant difference in the mean responses of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Lecturers on the extent to which hybrid teaching influence Postgraduate Educational Management students learning in Rivers State Universities. The z-calculated value of 1.67 was less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 ($1.67 \leq \pm 1.96$) for degree of freedom of 56 at .05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted which states that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Lecturers on the extent to which hybrid teaching influence Postgraduate Educational Management students learning in Rivers State Universities.

Discussion of Findings

The findings to research question 1 which focused on the extent to which face-to-face teaching influence Postgraduate Educational Management students learning in Rivers State Universities with grand mean of 3.06 for the RSU lecturers and 2.81 for the IAUE lecturers revealed that the respondents agreed to the statements that, face-to-face instruction encourages the sharing of knowledge; face-to-face learning builds confidence of teachers and learners ; face-to-face instruction enhances teacher/student interaction on the subject matter; it is used in solving analytical problems and face-to-face learning instruction is used to obtain reactions and feedbacks from students. So, the study revealed that face-to-face teaching to a high extent influence Postgraduate Educational Management students learning in Rivers State Universities. The finding was in agreement with the findings of Syvester (2013) that face-to-face instruction in Educational Management is normally fairly structured where lecturer and students meet at regularly scheduled times on the same days each week which limits flexibility with work and other activities. Teachers and students must generally be in class to get the teaching and learning experiences and to keep up with requirements.

Result on hypothesis 1 proved that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Lecturers on the extent to which face-to-face teaching influence Postgraduate Educational Management students learning in Rivers State Universities. This indicated that the respondents, Rivers State University and Ignatius

Ajuru University of Education Lecturers agreed to the fact that face-to-face teaching influence Postgraduate Educational Management students learning in Rivers State Universities.

The findings to research question 2 which focused on the extent to which hybrid teaching influence Postgraduate Educational Management students learning in Rivers State Universities with grand mean of 3.19 for the RSU lecturers and 2.79 for the IAUE lecturers revealed that the respondents agreed to the statements that, hybrid teaching promotes multiple interactions among lecturers and the students; hybrid teaching encourages the sharing of knowledge; it makes teaching and learning more flexible; it provides equal opportunities for discussion to introverts and extroverts and hybrid teaching increase interaction between the teachers and the students. Thus, the study revealed that hybrid teaching to a high extent influence Postgraduate Educational Management students learning in Rivers State Universities. The finding was in agreement with the findings of Freedom (2014) that online teaching takes place when the instructor (lecturer) and the learners (students) are not in the same physical location. It can also take place if the teacher and students are in this type of communication in an online learning is interactive in the sense that the students receive support and feedback from the teacher which may be immediate or delayed.

Result on hypothesis 2 proved that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Lecturers on the extent to which hybrid teaching influence Postgraduate Educational Management students learning in Rivers State Universities. This indicated that the respondents, Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Lecturers agreed to the fact that hybrid teaching influence Postgraduate Educational Management students learning in Rivers State Universities.

Conclusion

Based on the findings from the study, it is concluded that blended teaching enhances Postgraduate Educational Management Postgraduate students learning in Rivers State universities. Hence, its components such as face-to-face teaching and hybrid teaching to a high influence Postgraduate Educational Management students learning in Rivers State Universities to a high extent.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Lecturers should ensure that students or learners became active and not passive participants. This will help or make postgraduate Educational Management students to develop knowledge on their own and confident without the interference of the instructor or lecturer.
2. Measures should be adopted by lecturers on how online learning instruction could be used to achieve Educational Management courses having psychomotor objectives in Rivers State owned universities.

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